

ISic3700

I.Sicily inscription 3700

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object

tabula

(?)

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance**Coordinates**

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Catania

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140850

1. [— — —]αμαδίου {²⁷[Π]α[λλ]αδίου }²⁷ τοῦ
2. [— — — τ]ῆς Πελαγίας. ἐ[γ]-
3. [ενήθη] τῆ πρ (ὀ) ια' καλ (ανδῶν) [—]
4. [— — — —]#⁷, τελευτᾷ δ-
5. [ἐ τῆ πρὸ —' Σε]π[τ]εμβρίω.....V.....
{²⁷[μηνὶ Σε]π[τ]εμβρίωι }²⁷
6. [— — — κ]ὲ μόνανδρο-
7. [ς — — — — —] .
- 8.

Edition: PHI140851

1. [ἀγορασία Π]αλλαδίου τοῦ
2. [συμβίου τ]ῆς Πελαγίας· ἐ[γέ]-
3. [νετο Πελαγία] τῆ πρὸ ια' καλ [ανδ(ῶν)]
4. [— — — — —]., τελευτᾷ δ [ἐ]
5. [— — — — — Σε]πτεμβρίων.
6. [ἐνθάδε κίτ]ε μόνανδρο[ς].

7.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

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Bibliography

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